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#####
## Viewsheds of Nabataean Watchtowers within a 20km Radius around Petra
## =====
## Project: The Landscape Organization of the Petraean Hinterland in Nabataean-Roman Times
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## Version: 01
## Date of last changes: Sat 10. March 16:01:44 CET 2016
##
## Data: Military structures within the study area, SRTM1-DEM
## Author of data: Various (processed) survey data, own research of author
## Purpose: Viewsheds of military structures in the Petra area
## Content: Cumulative Viewsheds of Military Structures (based on Kennedy 2013, Kennedy 2016)
## Licence data: -
## Licence Script: -
##
##=====
## References
#####
## ref <- citation()
## citation(package="rgdal")
## citation(package="raster")
## citation(package="gdata")
## citation(package="sp")
## citation(package="rgrass7")
##
##=====
## Working Directory
#####
#
setwd("Y:/Archaeology/Promotion/Daten/Jordan/RASTER")
##=====
## Creating a Spatial Dataframe for Sites in R
#####
library(xlsx)
sites<- read.xlsx("./Viewsheds/Watchtowers_N/MASTER20160310_20KM_N_Watchtowers.xlsx", 1)
library(rgdal)
coordinates(sites) <- ~X_E_UTM+Y_N_UTM
proj4string(sites) <- CRS("+init=epsg:32636")
##=====
## Loading Base Data (DEM) Into R and Setting correct Projection
#####
library(raster)
dem<- raster("n30_e035_1arc_v3_clip2.tif")
dem <- projectRaster(dem, res=27.777778, crs=CRS("+init=epsg:32636"))
writeRaster(x = dem,
            filename = "SRTM1_Petra20km_UTM.tif", overwrite= TRUE)
##=====
## Creating Interface between GRASS 7 geographical information system and R
#####
library(rgrass7)
loc <- initGRASS("C:/Program Files (x86)/GRASS GIS 7.0.svn", home=getwd(), gisDbase = "GRASS_Temp", mapset =
"PERMANENT", override = TRUE)
execGRASS("g.proj", flags = c("c"), parameters = list(proj4="+init=epsg:32636"))
##=====
## Loading DEM into GRASS 7
#####
library(rgdal)
dem <- readGDAL("SRTM1_Petra20km_UTM.tif")

writeRAST(x = dem,
          vname="DEM",
          flags = c("overwrite"))
##=====
## Adjusting the region in GRASS 7
#####
execGRASS("g.region",
          parameters = list(rast = "DEM",
                            res = as.character(dem@grid@cellsize[1])))
##=====
## Checking the Region's Characteristics
#####
execGRASS("g.region", flags = c("p"))
##=====
## Generating Cumulative Viewsheds in GRASS 7 (Default Settings)
#####
parseGRASS("r.viewshed")
cum.view.sites <- brick(raster(dem))

for (i in seq(1, length(sites@coords[,1]))) {
  execGRASS("r.viewshed",
            flags = c("overwrite","b"),
            parameters = list(input = "DEM",
                              output = "view",
                              coordinates = sites@coords[i,],
                              obs_elev= 4,

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                tgt_elev= 4,
                max_dist=4400
            )
    )
    viewshed <- readRAST("view")
    cum.view.sites[[i]] <- raster(viewshed)
    names(cum.view.sites[[i]]) <- as.character(sites@data$Site_Name[i])
    cat("iteration ", i, " of ", length(sites@coords[,1]), "\n")

    writeRaster(cum.view.sites[[i]], paste("./Viewsheds/Watchtowers_N/Single_Viewsheds/Viewshed_nr_", i, ".tif"),
    format="GTiff", overwrite=TRUE)
  }
#####
## Plot
#####
##For single viewsheds:
plot(cum.view.sites[[3]])
## For cumulative viewsheds:
view.sum.sites <- sum(cum.view.sites)
plot(view.sum.sites)
```